

Implementation of the RESCHOOL project management process

The RESCHOOL Project Management Process has been successfully completed at month 10 (October 2023). The achievement of this milestone has supposed four major activities that have been reported in the respective deliverables. These are **i)** the development and implementation of an agile and responsive management process, including a detailed project management plan with the work breakdown structure and dependencies among the tasks of the project (*Deliverables D7.1 Project Management Handbook and D7.2 Project Management Plan*), **ii)** the definition of a data management plan, according to EU and National regulations, following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) management principles (*Deliverable D7.3 Data Management Plan*), **iii)** establishing working conditions that promote and monitor equal opportunities between men and women and considers gender issues in all the implementation aspects of the project (*Deliverable 7.4 Gender Action Plan*) and **iv)** the guidelines tackling ethical issues related to project activities with human participation (questionnaires, surveys, and interviews), privacy, and protection of personal data (*Deliverable D7.5 RESCHOOL ethical guidelines*).

About the RESCHOOL project

The EU funded RESCHOOL project aims to increase the active participation of communities in energy markets, enhancing and facilitating the management and trading of flexibility in cooperation with sectoral players. The project seeks to improve the way energy communities operate by enhancing the technology and behaviour of their users. This will help to make these communities more efficient and effective in their use of energy. You can stay up to date on the project's most important news, communications and events by following the [website](#) and the project's [LinkedIn](#) and [X/Twitter](#) pages.

Project Coordinator Joaquim Meléndez i Frigola Universitat de Girona Email: joaquim.melendez@udg.edu	Media contact RESCHOOL project Reza Dabirian European Science Communication Institute Email: rd@esci.eu
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